

Bayesian Networks for modelling concrete pavement deterioration

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Abstract

Understanding and predicting pavement deterioration is essential for effective road asset management yet remains challenging due to the complex and interacting influences of construction, material, traffic, and environmental factors. This study proposes a probabilistic modelling framework based on Bayesian Networks (BNs) combined with Gaussian copulas to analyse dependencies in heterogeneous road health monitoring data and to infer unobserved pavement performance indicators. Open-access data from the FHWA Long-Term Pavement Performance (LTPP) programme are used, focusing on Jointed Plain Concrete Pavements (JPCPs) without maintenance or rehabilitation interventions. A total of 1145 observations from 132 pavement sections are analysed, considering construction characteristics, traffic loading, climate variables, material properties, and key performance indicators including cracking, spalling, faulting, and roughness (IRI). The results reveal meaningful and interpretable dependency BN structures that are consistent with physical interpretation of pavement deterioration, while also highlighting non-intuitive relationships that need further investigation. The developed BN enables probabilistic inference of pavement condition based on partial observations, demonstrating its potential to support cost-effective monitoring and decision-making in pavement management. Overall, the study shows that BNs provide a powerful and flexible tool for modelling complex deterioration mechanisms in road infrastructure under uncertainty.

Keywords: Bayesian Networks; pavement deterioration; road health monitoring; copulas joint distribution; probabilistic inference

1 Introduction

Monitoring the health of road infrastructure is crucial for maintaining road safety and ensuring optimal performance over time [1]. Road health monitoring involves assessing surface condition, structural condition, and accessibility during severe weather events [2]. Performance indicators such as surface texture, cracking, faulting, and roughness are commonly measured using technologies including laser profilometers, Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR), smart vehicles, and embedded sensors [2, 3]. These technologies generate large volumes of heterogeneous data describing pavement structure, material properties, traffic loading, and environmental conditions. Effectively analysing these data to extract meaningful information on pavement deterioration remains a key challenge [4].

Understanding the relationships and dependencies among these variables is essential for interpreting deterioration mechanisms and supporting maintenance decisions. Traditional approaches often rely on regression analysis or pairwise correlations [5, 6], which typically assume independence among explanatory variables and focus on direct relationships only. As a result, such methods may not adequately capture the dependencies which are non-linear, indirect, and across multiple variables. Pavement deterioration, however, is governed by interacting mechanical, environmental, and material processes [7], motivating the use of probabilistic models capable of representing such interactions explicitly.

Bayesian Networks (BNs) provide a probabilistic graphical modelling framework suitable for analysing systems with interacting variables and uncertainty [8]. A BN represents the joint distribution of a set of random variables using a directed acyclic graph, in which nodes correspond to variables and directed edges encode conditional dependencies. One important advantage of BNs is their ability to handle heterogeneous multimodal data by using unit-free Copula joint distribution [9], which meets the need of handling various types of data from emerging monitoring techniques. Another advantage of BNs is to perform probabilistic inference [10], allowing unobserved variables to be estimated conditional on partial observations. This feature is particularly relevant for road infrastructure monitoring, where comprehensive measurements are often impractical or costly.

BNs have been increasingly applied in civil, hydraulic, and coastal engineering. For example, BNs have been used to characterize and quantify the spatial variability of deterioration in aging steel bridges [11], effectively capturing complex dependencies among structural condition variables. BNs have been used to model the conditional dependence between metocean variables and hydrodynamic forces acting on submerged floating tunnels [12]. In coastal engineering, BNs have been developed to probabilistically estimate wave overtopping on mound breakwaters [13], allowing the conditional distribution of structural response to be quantified rather than relying on deterministic predictions. These studies demonstrate the ability of BNs to capture dependence structures and support inference in engineering systems influenced by multiple interacting factors.

Although BNs have demonstrated strong potential, their application to pavement deterioration and road health monitoring remains relatively limited [14]. This study, first in literature, identifies correlations between multiple types of road data, including construction information, material properties, load and environmental condition, and deteriorations, and infer the deterioration based on available information. The open-access data from the FHWA Long-Term Pavement Performance (LTPP) programme [15] is used. The focus is on Jointed Plain Concrete Pavements (JPCPs) without maintenance or rehabilitation interventions. The results identify new insights on the influencing factors of pavement deterioration, demonstrate the suitability of BNs for probabilistically inferring the road deterioration.

2 Data

The dataset used in this study is sourced from the FHWA LTPP program [15]. Information on concrete pavements include details on pavement structure and construction, such as concrete thickness, base type, age, material properties, as well as climate, traffic, and pavement performance data. Figure 1 shows the LTPP data platform.

Figure 1 Screenshot of the LTPP data platform.

2.1 Data filtering

This paper focuses exclusively on concrete pavement data, specifically JPCPs. To eliminate the influence of maintenance and rehabilitation, only sections without any such interventions were considered. After applying these filters, 132 out of 2581 sections were selected. Most sections were surveyed over multiple years, resulting in a total of 1145 measurements collected across the country from 1991 to 2024. Figure 2 shows the locations of the selected sections on the map, provided by the LTPP data platform.

Figure 2 Screenshot of the selected sections' location shown by LTPP data platform.

2.2 Data distribution

Figure 3 shows the pairwise scatter plots of all the data. The histogram on the diagonal shows the empirical distribution of each variable. The studied variables include construction data, load and environment data, material property and performance data.

Construction data:

- the section age at the time of survey, noted as '1.'
- slab thickness in inches, noted as '3.'
- base thickness in inches, noted as '4.'
- base type, noted as '5.'

The distribution of age shows that most of the measurements were conducted at age less than 30 years, which meets the expected service lifetime of concrete pavement before repair. The distribution of slab thickness shows that two groups of pavements were surveyed, with one of thickness around 8.5 inches (21.59 cm) and the other 11 inches (27.94 cm). The distribution of base thickness shows two modes, with one around 4 inches (10.16 cm) and the other around 6 inches (15.24 cm). Bound and unbound bases were surveyed. Bound base is stiffer which generally performs better than unbound one. Not a clear pairwise correlation can be identified.

Load and environment data:

- Annual Average Daily Truck Traffic (AADTT), which counts the trucks in a year divided by 365 days, noted as '7.'
- Annual precipitation in mm, noted as '8.'
- Average annual temperature range in °C, which evaluates the difference between the hottest and the coldest months, taking monthly mean temperature recorded in a year, noted as '9.'
- The freezing index, which estimates the effect from winter temperature and is calculated as the cumulative degree-days below freezing over a certain period, noted as '10.'

The bimodal shape of annual precipitation suggests that the surveyed sections are divided between regions with relatively low and moderate-to-high precipitation levels. The skewed distribution of freezing index shows that most pavement sections experience little to no freezing conditions, while a smaller number of sections are exposed to higher freezing conditions.

Material properties:

- tensile strength of concrete in psi, noted as '15.'

The tensile strength centered around 500 psi (~3 MPa), with a smaller number of sections exhibiting very high or low tensile strength.

Pavement performance data:

- number of transverse cracks, noted as '17.',
- length of longitudinal cracks in m, noted as '18.',
- length of spalling in m, noted as '21.',
- average wheel path fault in mm, noted as '24.',
- IRI in m/km, noted as '27.'.

Figure 3 Distribution of the variables including (1.) age at the time of survey, (3.) slab thickness in inches, (4.) base thickness in inches, (5.) base type, (7.) Annual Average Daily Truck Traffic (AADTT), (8.) annual precipitation in mm, (9.) average annual temperature range, (10.) freezing index, (15.) tensile strength in psi, (17.) length of longitudinal cracks in m, (18.) number of transverse cracks, (21.) length of spalling in m, (24.) average wheel path fault in mm and (27.) IRI in m/km.

Most of sections had little transverse cracks, a spalling length less than 5 meters, very low wheel path fault values, with a large peak from 0 to 0.5 mm, and IRI values between 1 and 2 m/km. Very few sections exhibit IRI values greater than 2.5 m/km.

Some variables demonstrate a correlation such as IRI increases with age but many of the correlations are not clear. It is also shown that the data is a mix of discrete (base type – bound and unbound) and continuous (the rest). In the following paper, the data from sections with unbound and bound base type are studied separately.

3 Modelling approach

3.1 Copulas

The dependence between two datasets is typically measured using covariance or correlation.

$$Cov(X_1, X_2) = E([X_1 - E(X_1)][X_2 - E(X_2)]) \quad (1)$$

$$\rho(X_1, X_2) = \frac{Cov(X_1, X_2)}{\sigma_{X_1}\sigma_{X_2}} \quad (2)$$

where $\rho(X_1, X_2) = -1$ means the perfect linear negative dependence, $\rho(X_1, X_2) = 0$ means independence, and $\rho(X_1, X_2) = 1$ means the perfect linear positive dependence.

The drawbacks of measuring dependence using covariance or correlation are: (1) variations in the marginal distributions between datasets, and (2) the fact that the bivariate distribution is not unique.

Another type of measurement, known as Spearman correlation, evaluates the correlation between ranked data. Ranking transforms the data into a uniform distribution on (0,1) through cumulative distributions.

$$F_X(\mathbf{x}) = F_{X_1, X_2}(x_1, x_2) = C_\theta(F_{X_1}(x_1), F_{X_2}(x_2)) \quad (3)$$

$$\hat{F}_X(x) = \frac{\text{number of samples} \leq x}{\text{total number of samples}} \quad (4)$$

A copula is a distribution on the unit square with uniform marginal distributions. Random variables X_1 and X_2 are joined by copula C . Every continuous bivariate distribution can be represented in terms of a copula. Moreover, for any continuous joint distribution, there is always a unique copula that corresponds to it. This paper uses Gaussian copula.

3.2 Bayesian Network

Figure 4 shows the structure of the developed BN. Each node represents a variable, with grey colour on construction data, orange on load and environment data, green on material properties, and blue on performance indicators. The immediate predecessors and successors of a node are referred to as ‘parents’ and ‘children’ respectively, showing the cause and effect. To study information about a variable, its predecessors (parents) should be considered first. Nodes without parents are characterized by marginal distributions, while nodes with parents are represented by conditional distributions. The arrangement of nodes is based on the prior knowledge of the pavement deterioration and its influential factors.

Figure 4 illustration of the BN structure.

4 Results and discussion

4.1 Measurement of dependence

Figure 5a exemplifies the dependence measured by covariance in the data of pavement age and IRI. Each point in the scatter plot represents a pavement section, with its age on the x -axis and its corresponding Average IRI on the y -axis. Average IRI is the average of the IRI on the left wheel path and the right wheel path. Most sections were less than 30 years old, with an average age of around 14 years. And most sections had IRI less than 2, with an average value of around 1. From the raw data, hardly any correlation is found between the two variables.

Figure 5b measures the relationship of the same dataset using Spearman correlation which uses ranked data. The red curves highlight the positive relationship between the two variables, suggesting that older pavements generally tend to have higher roughness, but with considerable variability. The red circle shows that a cluster of young sections had low roughness. Comparing Figure 5b with Figure 5a, a clearer positive correlation pattern can be found from Spearman correlation using the ranked data.

Figure 5 Relationship between pavement age and IRI: (a) in raw data and (b) in ranked data.

4.2 Correlations in the variables in pavement sections

Figure 6 shows the Spearman rank correlation coefficients (ρ) between pairs of variables measured in pavement sections with unbound base. The colour scale on the right indicates the strength and direction of correlations, with red representing stronger positive correlations, blue representing stronger negative correlations, and green/yellow representing weaker correlations.

Significant correlations ($|\rho| > 0.18$) are highlighted in red, indicating noteworthy relationships between variables. Several correlations are consistent with engineering expectations. Longitudinal crack length shows a positive correlation with pavement age ($\rho = 0.44$), reflecting material deterioration over time, and with freezing index ($\rho = 0.25$), suggesting the influence of freeze–thaw cycles. A negative correlation is observed between longitudinal crack length and base thickness ($\rho = -0.36$), indicating that thinner bases may provide insufficient support, leading to increased cracking, potentially due to differential settlement or moisture-related effects. Another negative correlation is observed between longitudinal crack length and annual precipitation ($\rho = -0.23$), indicating that more rain may reduce the longitudinal crack, potentially due to better early-stage curing. Transverse cracking is positively correlated with AADTT ($\rho = 0.33$), which is consistent with increased damage under heavier traffic loading. Average wheel path faulting shows positive correlations with both age ($\rho = 0.32$) and AADTT ($\rho = 0.21$), reflecting the combined effects of material degradation and traffic loading. In addition, IRI on the right wheel path is negatively correlated with the tensile strength ($\rho = -0.26$), suggesting that higher strength contributes to increased surface roughness.

Some correlations are less straightforward and need further investigation. Spalling length shows a negative correlation with AADTT ($\rho = -0.44$), indicating that traffic loading may not be the primary driver of spalling in these sections.

Figure 6 Correlation coefficients using bivariate Gaussian Copulas for pavement sections with unbound base type.

Following the same methods, Figure 7 shows the Spearman rank correlation coefficients (ρ) between pairs of variables measured in pavement sections with bound base.

Several correlations are consistent with engineering expectations. Longitudinal crack length is positively correlated with base thickness ($\rho = 0.34$), which may be attributed to the stiffer support provided by bound bases, leading to higher tensile stresses in the concrete slabs. In addition, longitudinal cracking is positively correlated with annual precipitation ($\rho = 0.18$), likely due to increased moisture infiltration and weakening of the support layers; the low correlation with freezing index ($\rho = -0.06$) suggests that freeze-thaw effects are not the dominant mechanism in this case. Longitudinal cracking shows little correlation with AADTT ($\rho = -0.05$), indicating that traffic loading is not the primary driver.

Transverse cracking is positively correlated with both base thickness ($\rho = 0.25$) and freezing index ($\rho = 0.39$), suggesting that stiffer support conditions and freeze-thaw action contribute to crack development. Spalling is positively correlated with age ($\rho = 0.19$), indicating the deterioration due to aging. Average wheel path faulting increases with pavement age ($\rho = 0.27$), reflecting progressive deterioration, and decreases with base thickness ($\rho = -0.2$), consistent with the restraining effect of a stiffer base on vertical deformation. IRI on the right wheel path is positively correlated with age ($\rho = 0.34$) and with surface damage indicators, including longitudinal cracks ($\rho = 0.26$), transverse cracks ($\rho = 0.3$), and spalling length ($\rho = 0.55$), confirming that accumulated surface damage leads to increased roughness.

Some correlations are less straightforward and require further investigation. Spalling length shows a negative correlation with AADTT ($\rho = -0.24$), a trend observed for both bound and unbound base types. In addition, average wheel path faulting is negatively correlated with transverse cracking ($\rho = -0.28$) and spalling length ($\rho = -0.36$), and IRI on the right wheel is negatively related with the average wheel path fault ($\rho = -0.19$). This relationship is likely indirect, as faulting is negatively correlated with base thickness, whereas cracking and spalling are positively correlated with base thickness, suggesting that base characteristics may be influencing these correlations rather than a direct causal link.

Figure 8 shows the results of test of goodness of fit for four types of Copulas, which are Clayton (Cl), Frank (Fr), Gaussian (Ga) and Gumble (Gu). The goodness of fit is evaluated by the Cramer-von Mises statistic (the sum of squared difference between the parametric and empirical copulas). Lower value indicates a better fit. Though Gaussian Copula did not perform the best for every pair of parameters, generally this type of Copula is optimal.

Figure 7 Correlation coefficients using bivariate Gaussian Copulas for pavement sections with bound base type.

Figure 9 presents the BN for the variables in pavement sections with a bound base type. Only relationships with significant correlations are shown, where the absolute value of the correlation coefficient (ρ) exceeds 0.2.

Figure 9 BN with identified correlations for sections with bound base type.

4.3 Bayesian Network inference based on evidence

The BN is conditionalized on different values of the construction data, load and climate data, and material properties using the values presented in Table 1. These values are taken from measurement of one section.

Table 1 The measured data for predictions

	Age [year]	Slab Thickness [inches]	Base Thickness [inches]	AADTT	Annual Precipitation [mm]	Freezing Index [-]	Tensile Strength [psi]
Data for predictions	32	9.3	3.5	340	1257.5	8	500

The estimated distribution of the pavement performance, namely the length of longitudinal cracks, number of transverse cracks, length of spalling, average wheel path fault and IRI right, are shown in Figure 10. The blue bars show the estimated distribution without considering the measurement data, the orange bars are the distribution conditionalized by the measurement, and the blue dots show the actual values. It can be found that the conditionalized distribution is closer to the actual values compared to that estimated without considering the measurement: the conditionalized distribution of number of transverse cracks (Figure 10b) is more concentrated around the actual value, and the conditionalized distribution of average wheel path fault (Figure 10d) and IRI (Figure 10e) are shifted towards the actual value.

Figure 10 Distribution of the pavement performance with bound base type: Unconditional prediction (blue bars), conditionalized on the measured data shown in Table 1 (orange bars), and the actual value (blue circle).

5 Conclusion

This study explored the identification of correlations in road health monitoring data using BNs, with a focus on the relationships between key pavement performance indicators, material properties, load and environmental conditions, and construction data. The application of copulas allowed for the modelling of dependencies between variables with non-linear interactions, and the study utilized data from the FHWA LTPP program to examine concrete pavement sections with both bound and unbound base types.

Several important correlations were identified, such as the positive relationship between pavement age and longitudinal crack length, and the influence of annual precipitation and freezing index on crack formation. The analysis also revealed that bound base types, while offering stiffer support, contributed to increased cracking due to stress concentration. Additionally, the findings indicated that environmental factors, including temperature variations and precipitation, significantly impacted pavement performance over time. Interestingly, some

dependencies shown by the data/observations did not meet expectations, such as the negative relationship between spalling length and traffic load, require further investigation.

Moreover, BNs enable probabilistic inference of unobserved pavement performance indicators based on a limited subset of measured variables. This means that not all indicators need to be measured simultaneously to obtain an estimate of pavement condition. As a result, BNs have the potential to reduce the cost and effort associated with extensive instrumentation and data collection in road health monitoring.

Future research can focus on expanding the dataset and refining the modelling approach to address unexplained correlations and further improve the predictive capabilities of the network.

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